

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Rinchen**FIRST NAME:** Namgay**PROGRAM CODE:** DBIO**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 07%

The author used the software Microsoft 360 version 16 on Windows 11

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. what are the two kinds of research problems in Turabian's framework?

- Qualitative and quantitative
- Practical and conceptual.¹**
- Historical and contemporary
- Local and global

2. What does Turabian say is the most effective way to avoid plagiarism?

- Using quotes whenever possible
- Keeping detailed notes and citing all sources properly.²**

¹ Kate L Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed. (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 29.

² Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 51.

- Avoiding the use of secondary sources
 - Using paraphrases instead of quotes
3. According to Turabian, where should the complete source citation be included using the author-date style?
- In the footnotes
 - In a works cited page
 - In the text, immediately after the author's name
 - In the reference list at the end of the paper.**³
4. According to Turabian, when is it appropriate to use block quotations?
- For any quotation over three lines long
 - When the quotation is five lines or longer.**⁴
 - Only for quotations from historical documents
 - Only in book-length dissertations
5. Which of the following is true about the Chicago citation style when handling quotes?
- It requires that all reference citations appear outside of the quoted material.
 - It allows for reference citations to be omitted or inserted within the quoted material.**⁵

³ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 235.

⁴ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 371.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 49.

- It prohibits the omission of reference citations within quotes.
 - It mandates that citations must always be included inside the quoted material.
6. where is the literature review most commonly placed in a typical dissertation structure?
- In the introduction as a subsection.
 - Before the introduction as a preliminary section.
 - As a separate chapter following the introduction.**⁶
 - In the conclusion as a summary.
7. When a situation requires both a comma and a stronger punctuation mark, such as a question mark or a dash, what is the correct punctuation rule to follow?
- Use both the comma and the stronger punctuation mark together.
 - Omit the stronger punctuation mark and use the comma.
 - Omit the comma and use only the stronger punctuation mark.**⁷
 - Use a semicolon instead of the comma and the stronger punctuation mark.
8. When should a semicolon be used in a compound sentence?
- To separate independent clauses connected by coordinating conjunctions like “and” or “but.”
 - To separate dependent clauses regardless of conjunctions.

⁶ James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 31.

⁷ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 325.

- To separate independent clauses that are not connected by a coordinating conjunction.⁸**
- To replace a comma in simple sentences.
9. According to the Turabian style, how should you modify a quotation if the original passage ends with a colon or semicolon?
- Leave the colon or semicolon unchanged, regardless of the sentence structure.
- Delete the colon or semicolon, or change it to a period or comma based on your sentence structure.⁹**
- Always change it to a colon to match the original passage.
- Replace the colon or semicolon with a dash for better clarity.
10. How should fractional and whole numbers be presented when used together for the same type of item in a sentence or paragraph?
- Write the whole numbers as words and the fractions as numerals.
- Write both the whole numbers and fractions as words.
- Give both whole numbers and fractions as numerals.¹⁰**
- Use fractions as numerals and whole numbers as words.

⁸ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 320.

⁹ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 376.

¹⁰ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 342.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.